

Morbidity and Mortality projects: Mortality

1. Heart Disease
 - a. The transcriptome of the plaque
 - b. The foam cell transcriptome: differentiation of the macrophage to the foam cell
 - c. Transcriptional responses to oxLDL
 - d. Defining markers of risk in the blood in humans with high CRP
2. Stroke
 - a. Mouse Models of Cerebral Infarction
 - b. The transcriptional signature of stroke in humans in the brain.
 - c. Hypoxia in the brain
3. Cancer
 - a. Solid Tumors
 - i. Breast
 1. The primary tumor
 - a. Tumor biology
 - b. Therapeutic targets
 2. Lymph Node metastasis
 - a. Tumor biology
 - b. Therapeutic targets
 3. Metastasis to distant sites: tumor biology and therapeutic targets (catalytic and non-catalytic)
 - a. Brain
 - b. Lungs
 - c. Liver
 - d. Bones
 4. Subtype-specific biology: (e.g., tumor epigenome, genes associated with survival)
 - a. Luminal A/B
 - b. Basal-subtype
 - c. TNBC
 - d. Claudin
 5. Resistance
 - a. Basal-subtype
 - b. TNBC
 - c. HR+
 - ii. Lung
 1. The primary tumor
 - a. Tumor biology
 - b. Therapeutic targets
 2. Lymph Node metastasis
 - a. Tumor biology
 - b. Therapeutic targets
 3. Metastasis to distant sites: tumor biology and therapeutic targets (catalytic and non-catalytic)
 - a. Brain
 - b. Lymph nodes

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- ii. Prostate
- iii. Melanoma
- iv. HPV-positive cancers
 1. Cervical
 2. Head and Neck

General Cancer Biology

Oncogenes

Ras

Raf

Tumor suppressors

p53

Rb1

Apc

MSH2

Transformation

Growth factors

Homeobox transcription factors

The ES cell program and solid tumors

ECT2, a solid tumor gene product and marker of transformation

Senescence

The senescence program

Cell-intrinsic

Cell-extrinsic

The senescence bypass program: overriding cell cycle restriction

Interactions with the environment and pathogens enhance transformation by

promoting senescence bypass:

cigarette smoke (lung cancer),

bacteria: salmonella typhi (gallbladder cancer)

H. pylori (gastric cancer)

Tumor Cell Biology

Nutrient sensing, energy and the secretory pathway: TSC and TBD families

mTOR and Akt

Disease progression and disease modifiers

Genetic background

TNBC in white women and in black women

BRCA1/2

Defining the transcriptional basis to cancer predisposition in humans with

BRCA mutation

Resistance and gene signatures associated with treatment failure

Resistance associated with specific chemotherapies

Resistance in specific disease types

Complete response versus partial response or progressive disease

Genes whose expression compensates for medical interventions in cancer:

compensatory kinase induction during growth factor inhibition (e.g., ERBB2, VEGF-A)

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Translational Medical Oncology: Understanding mechanism of action to support enhanced treatment of humans with cancer

PARP1/2

CDK4/6

PI3K

Xist, a novel entity in human cancer

Xist expression and activity immediately prior to and during transformation

Xist in subtype selection

Xist in PAM50 subtype

Xist in NSCLC

Xist in disease resistance

Xist in metastasis

4. Diabetes

- a. Integrating iPS models of Diabetes with the diabetic pancreatic transcriptome to understand the diabetes transcriptome
- b. Identification of activators of insulin production using heterologous expression systems

5. Pulmonary Disease (emphysema and COPD)

- a. Defining the COPD transcriptome in the human lung
- b. Chemokine biology in the blood and epithelial cells of the lung

6. Alzheimer's Disease

- a. iPS models of Alzheimer's Disease
 - i. PSEN
 - ii. APOE3/E4
- b. The Alzheimer's transcriptome in the human brain: region-specific transcription
 - i. Whole brain transcription by stage of disease progression and location
- c. Therapeutic targets in Alzheimer's: addressing the Tau fibril (neurofibrillary tangle) and COMT activation
 - i. Proteasome pathway targets
 - ii. Targets in the secretory pathway

7. Kidney Disease

- a. Hypertension
- b. Chronic Kidney Disease
- c. Diabetic nephropathy

8. Liver Disease

- a. Hepatitis C/Hepatitis B
 - i. Novel therapeutic targets in Hepatitis
- b. Fatty Liver Disease/NASH
- c. Alcoholic liver disease